

Sound Asleep: A study on the relationship between emotional state and sound preferences as sleep aid

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ABSTRACT

Sleep plays a vital role in our lives, yet many people experience sleep deprivation and sleep disorders that prevent them from getting adequate rest and being able to function well during the day. Not feeling emotionally well can be the cause of sleep deprivation. This study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional state and individual sound preferences to fall asleep. The study focuses on environmental sounds rather than music as the use of these sounds for sleep is under-explored. An online survey was conducted to assess whether people prefer different sounds to aid sleep depending on their emotional state. The results show that sounds such as Rain, Underwater sounds, and Singing Bowl sounds are preferred for negative emotional states. On the other hand, the sounds of Birds, Crickets, and Rain are selected more often for positive emotional states. Additionally, the paper describes the initial stages of a mobile app development that we are planning to use to implement the study's findings. The app asks the user for their emotional state and suggests to them three different sounds to regulate their emotional state and help them fall asleep.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sleep is one of the most essential aspects of life. We need sleep to perform our daily activities and maintain cognitive function and body health [1]. There are many reasons for sleep deprivation and sleep disorders. However, one of the causes is the individual's emotional state before falling asleep. [2]. Listening to music is effective in regulating emotion and reducing stress [3]. Many people also listen to sounds to help them fall asleep.

This study looks at the relationship between emotional state and how that might influence the sounds that one chooses to aid sleep. A survey was conducted to collect data from participants. The survey was constructed so that participants could rank different environmental sounds in terms of their preference when they imagined feeling a particular emotion before sleeping. Additionally, the paper proposes a prototype of a sleeping app that uses the data from the survey to recommend different sounds to the user

to aid sleep depending on the user's emotional state. The goal of the broader project is to develop a practical sound-based applications to help people regulate their emotional state and help them fall asleep.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1 Impact of Sleep Quality on Health

Sleep is essential for mental health, mood, cognitive function, heart, brain, and general physical health [1]. Insufficient sleep and untreated sleeping disorders are destructive to our health and well-being [1]. A systematic review [4] of 277 studies revealed that short sleep latencies, minimal awakenings, and no or few awakenings after sleep onset characterize good sleep quality. A sleep survey with 1000 students found that those categorized as having good quality sleep recorded fewer negative moods (depression, confusion, anger, and fatigue) throughout the day than those with bad-quality sleep [5]. In another study, participants experienced decreased sleepiness during the day in weekly and daily measures by increasing the duration of sleep during the night by 43 minutes per night [6].

Sleep deprivation and sleep disorders are on the rise in modern society [7, 8]. Sleep deprivation leads to a range of mental and physical health issues. A night of poor sleep can affect short-term memory [9]. The emotional state of a person can also be affected by sleep loss. Research shows reduced activation and happiness throughout the day when participants experience one or two nights of bad sleep, together with increased anger, depression, and fatigue [10]. People who experience poor quality sleep throughout the week have also reported high levels of stress compared to people with good quality sleep [5].

Insomnia is the most common sleep disorder [11]. Individuals who experience insomnia report difficulties falling asleep, returning to sleep after experiencing a nocturnal awakening, and experiencing fatigue when awakening in the morning [12]. The presence of sleep disorders and their consequential impact on mental and physical well-being in humans underscores the need to obtain good quality sleep.

2.2 Sleep Enhancement

Due to the widespread occurrence of sleep problems and their potential impact on human health, several sleep enhancement interventions, both pharmacological and not, have been suggested in scientific studies. Pharmacolog-

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15032113>

ical interventions such as medicinal interventions are often used, but provide a short-term solution. Additionally, there are some concerns about long-term use of these medications, due to the risk of side effects, abuse, and dependence [13–15]. Non-pharmacological methods, on the other hand, are more sustainable in the long term and do not have apparent side effects [16, 17]. These include hot baths, breathing techniques, and stretching before bed [18].

Another widely used technique is auditory stimulation, which has been shown to improve sleep quality. Some of these stimuli include the use of white and pink noise, as well as music, binaural beats, natural sounds, sound synchronization, etc [19, 20]. A sound-augmented blanket has been shown to be effective in promoting relaxation and potentially improving sleep quality [21]. However, research on the relationship between auditory stimuli to aid sleep and the emotional states experienced during the day and at the onset of sleep is significantly lacking. Specifically, understanding which types of auditory stimulation are most beneficial for sleep based on specific emotions remains underexplored.

2.3 Emotions, sound and sleep

Emotions can have a direct impact on people’s sleep quality. Negative emotions have been shown to produce a decrease in sleep efficiency, total sleep, and percentage of REM (rapid eye movement) sleep, and increase awakenings [2]. The use of auditory stimulation is effective in affecting emotions and can potentially improve sleep quality. For example, Juslin and Sloboda [22] showed that soft, unchanging music evokes feelings of peace, while slow tempos induce tranquility. Research indicates that people often use music before bedtime to regulate emotions and alleviate negative thoughts [3]. Moreover, exposure to pink noise during sleep has been associated to stabilizing emotional states and promoting deep sleep [23]. Active auditory stimulation at night has shown promise in reducing cortisol levels and mitigating stress [24, 25]. Similarly, subjects exposed to binaural beats coupled with natural sounds have been shown to experience diminished negative emotional states such as tension, anger, and depression [26]. Furthermore, personal preferences have been shown to be important when it comes to sound. To help customize music to individual preferences, one study [27] developed four sleep music profiles based on sleep engagement and music openness. Despite these useful findings, there remains a gap in understanding how auditory stimuli can be tailored to individuals’ emotional states during sleep onset.

This project investigates individuals’ preferences for sounds conducive to sleep when experiencing various emotional states, and describes the initial prototype for an app that suggests sounds for sleep on the basis of a person’s emotional state before sleep. The focus of this project is specifically on environmental sounds as this type of stimuli, and its relation to emotions and sleep, is particularly understudied.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 4 describes the listening test conducted to identify as-

sociations between emotional state and preferred sounds for sleep; Section 6 describes an initial prototype for a sleep enhancing app that, based on the user’s emotional state, suggests different sounds for aiding sleep; Sections 7 and 8 discuss the results and conclude respectively.

3. METHOD

An online survey was conducted to identify people’s sleep habits and their sound preferences given a particular emotional state. Based on these results, an initial prototype for a sleep app is proposed.

4. ONLINE SURVEY

A survey was conducted to determine whether the choice of sound for sleep could depend on the emotional state a person is experiencing. In the survey, participants were asked to answer questions about their sleep habits and their use of sound as a sleep aid. They were then asked to imagine feeling a particular emotion and rank different sounds in terms of whether they would choose them as a sleeping aid when feeling that emotion. For simplicity, we have chosen four emotions to cover each quadrant of the circumplex model of emotions [28]. These are: *Happy*, *Sad*, *Calm*, and *Stressed*. *Happy* represents high arousal with a positive valence; *Sad*, low arousal with a negative valence; *Calm*, low arousal with a positive valence; and *Stressed*, high arousal with a negative valence.

4.1 Survey structure

The survey contained a subset of the *Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index* questions [29] to gather information about participants’ sleep habits. Participants who relied on sound for sleep were asked detailed questions about the kind of sounds they would usually listen to. Subsequently, participants were instructed to imagine themselves experiencing a given emotion before sleep, and rank six different sounds placing on top the sound they thought would help them relax and fall asleep. The emotional states and sounds were presented in a randomized order to minimize order effects. All audio stimuli were normalized to -30 LUFS in Audacity¹. At the start of the test, participants were required to put headphones on, listen to a short audio file of white noise at -30 LUFS, adjust their audio volume to a comfortable level, and then they were explicitly asked to maintain this level throughout the test. At the end of each ranking, participants had the opportunity to write free text comments to explain their ranking choices.

4.2 Stimuli

Six sounds were chosen based on the research literature [19, 20] about the types of sounds people use for sleeping. They were categorized into three different groups: Pitched sounds, Natural sounds, and Animal sounds. Each category contained two different sounds. These were chosen on the basis of research on sound and emotions [22]. In particular: slow tempos, soft volumes and little loudness

¹ <https://www.audacityteam.org>

variation are associated with tranquil, soft and peaceful states, with higher pitched sounds being associated with more serene states and lower pitched sounds with more tranquil states. Chimes and Singing Bowls were chosen as examples of higher and lower pitched sounds, respectively. Birds and Crickets were chosen to represent softness by having soft volumes and little dynamic variation. Rain and Underwater sounds were chosen as natural sounds with differing slow tempos.

4.3 Participants

We recruited a total of 78 participants. Twenty-one people were recruited from our close social network, while the remaining 57 were recruited from the Prolific online platform². In this paper, we will refer to these groups as *Local Group* and *Global group*, respectively. Local Group is divided into 9 males and 12 females, with average age 26 and a standard deviation (SD) of 6.1 all living in Sweden. Global Group is divided into 30 males and 27 females, with average age 29 and SD of 8.2, and recruited from across the globe, including regions such as Africa, South America, North America, Europe, and Asia. Extending the test to Prolific allowed us to recruit participants of different ages and genders, from all over the world, and with no connection to the researchers, reducing potential bias and increasing the reliability of the results.

At the start of the survey, participants were asked how they felt and the results of participants who declared feeling emotionally unwell were excluded from the study. Prolific participants were recruited with the following screening criteria: half males, half female, without hearing difficulties, without diagnosed or ongoing mental health issues such as depression. All participants were provided with information about the survey before starting and were explicitly informed that they could withdraw at any time. The Local Group did the test without compensation. The Global Group was compensated with the standard hourly rate of 9£ pro-rata.

5. RESULTS

5.1 Sleep habits

The results show that sleep habits were relatively similar between the groups. The majority, 59, answered that they had fairly good sleep during the past month, with only 19 reporting fairly poor sleep. Local Group reported having an average of 6.2 hours of sleep, while Global Group had 6.7 hours daily in the past month. When asked whether they slept alone or with someone else, 41 participants said that they slept by themselves (14 participants from the Local Group and 27 from the Global Group). Two of these people wrote that they share the room with their pets. Listening to sound as a sleep aid was relatively common among our participants, with 45 out of 78 people reporting that they occasionally or regularly use sound to facilitate sleep. The majority declared that they prefer to listen to sounds with words in them, such as podcasts, audiobooks, music

²<https://www.prolific.com>

Figure 1. The *Left* plot illustrates the frequency of sound usage for sleep among participants. Note that the Global Group's counts are divided by 2.7 (N of subject in Global/N of subjects in Local) to make them comparable to the Local Group. The *Right* plot details the types of sounds used among participant.

Figure 2. These figures illustrate the responses from the listening test's ranking questions on sound preferences associated with four different emotions: Stressed, Happy, Sad, and Calm. For each emotion, the bars represent the number of participants who ranked each sound type as their first and second choices according to which group they belong.

with lyrics, TV programs, and Yoga Nadra meditation. In comparison, fewer people declared listening to instrumental music, natural sounds, and ASMR.

5.2 Ranking sounds in relation to emotional state

Figure 2 shows the ranking of all the sounds for all the emotions when we sum the counts for the first and second choice (e.g., for Happy: the Rain sound has been ranked first 9 times and second 0 times, so the sum is 9). Note that the Global counts are made comparable to the Local counts by dividing them by 2.7, i.e. the ratio between the participants in the Local group and the participants in the Global Group.

Overall, the results of the Local Group and the Global Group are fairly similar, confirming the absence of bias due to the different recruitment methods. The sound of Rain was preferred by both groups across emotions, and the sound of Chimes was the least preferred by both groups regardless of the emotion. The main difference between the two groups can be noticed as the Crickets sound is consistently preferred more often by the Local Group rather than the Global Group. Additionally, the Chimes sound is chosen more often by the Global Group, compared to the

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater-Singing Bowls, Birds-Crickets

Table 1. Top 3 sound choices dependent on emotional state.

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
	FEMALE (39 people)
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Singing Bowls, Crickets-Birds
Calm	Rain, Birds , Singing Bowl-Crickets
	MALE (39 people)
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Crickets
Sad	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowl-Crickets

Table 2. Top 3 sound choices by gender, the text in **bold** indicates the main differences between the two genders.

Local Group.

Both groups show a change in sound preference depending on the emotional state. When looking at the differences between Positive and Negative emotions, we see that the Underwater sound is ranked relatively high by both groups in relation to negative emotional states (Stressed and Sad). And generally the Local and Global profiles for the Negative emotions are similar. The profiles for the Positive emotions show more differences between groups, but the Birds sound is rated high for the Happy emotion for both groups.

As we mentioned above, the Local Group shows a higher preference for the Crickets sound than Global Group. This preference is relatively stronger in the positive states, in particular the Happy state.

Both Local and Global Groups rated the Underwater and the Singing Bowl sound high in the Stress state. Local Group rates them particularly high in the Sad state too.

To summarize, and combining the results from both tests, in Table 1 are the sounds preferred for each emotion.

5.3 Further Analyses

In Table 2 we report the results by gender.

In this study, male participants seem to prefer the Underwater sound for low arousal emotions (Sad and Calm), while female participants seem to prefer Birds and Crickets sounds.

In Table 3, we can see the results split between participants who use audio as sleep aid in their sleep routine, and participants who never use an audio as sleep aid.

Participants who use audio as sleep aid seem to prefer Singing Bowl and Birds sounds across various emotions, while those who do not use audio as sleep aid seem to

Emotion	Top 3 Sound Choices
	AUDIO AID (45 people)
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Birds, Singing Bowls-Crickets
Sad	Rain, Singing Bowls, Crickets-Birds
Calm	Rain, Birds, Singing Bowl
	NO AUDIO AID (33 people)
Stressed	Rain, Underwater, Singing Bowls
Happy	Rain, Crickets-Birds, Underwater
Sad	Rain, Underwater , Singing Bowls
Calm	Rain, Underwater, Crickets

Table 3. Top 3 sound choices for people who use audio as sleep aid vs. people who do not. The text in **bold** indicates the main differences between the two groups.

choose more often the Underwater sound across several emotional states.

5.4 Summary of comments

Twenty three participants from the Global Group and three from the Local Group commented on their choices of sound. Two participants mentioned how some sounds brought back memories. For example, the sound of Crickets reminded some people of a safe place or time on an island, something that helped them calm down when feeling stressed. Three people linked sounds with objects or seasons. For example, a person rated the Crickets' sound high when feeling sad because crickets reminded them of summer, which made them happy. Another person preferred water sounds (Underwater and Rain) when feeling happy because they felt closer to nature. Two people mentioned that birds are associated with early morning, and therefore not the first choice for falling asleep:

Sometimes, hearing birds chirping in the morning reminds me of camping. However, it also brings back memories of how early we had to wake up for activities, which can be a bit of a buzzkill.

Some participants mentioned that the Underwater sound made them feel trapped and anxious. Participants who rated Birds and Crickets high for Sad feelings mentioned that these sounds cheered them up, while the Rain and Singing Bowl sounds made them feel even more sad. Rain and Crickets sounds were mainly described as peaceful sounds. The Chimes were the least favorite of all sounds, although some people did rate them high for positive moods, and were generally described as noisy and too loud. Below are selected comments about each emotion.

In terms of soothing a Sad emotional state, one participant stated: *"Light" sounds (Chimes, Birds) feel good while being in a bad mood, as they are capable of disrupting the bad mood* Another participant stated: *The rain has that calming effect, but when one is sad it also promises better days to come. To me, rain signifies cleaning of the air and growth of vegetables, which is a promise in itself. Birds sounds promise a better day as they mostly chirp when the skies are beautiful with no disturbing weather,*

so they also bring hope.

In addressing a Stressed state one person stated: *Birds are too lively to calm me while stressed, same goes for crickets. The Underwater sound, and especially Rain, seems natural and can make me calm.*

Two comments exemplify the ambivalent feelings towards the Underwater sound: *Water sounds are my thing* versus *Nothing will ever make me enjoy the sound of the ocean or any underwater sound.*

Regarding the Happy emotion, one person stated: *Living creatures seem like a good addition to a happy mood because they seem happy to be alive, so birds and crickets are fine.*

The comments on the Calm state are very varied, reflecting the main results of the study (see Table 1) *Chimes, Birds are relaxing; Crickets with Rain seems natural and easy to blend in calm mood, the underwater sounds are calming, I feel like the singing bowls would help keep me feeling calm.*

Finally, a person stated that: *The quickest I get to fall asleep is when I'm calm, and at this stage I might not need any sound to help me sleep.*

Overall, the survey showed that there is a relationship between emotional state and sound choices for sleep. Based on these findings, we developed an app prototype aiming to suggest to users the perfect sound, tailored to their emotional state, to improve sleep.

6. SOUND ASLEEP - APP DEVELOPMENT

Research shows that many people use smartphone apps to improve their sleep, and most apps aim to reduce sleep latency through auditory stimuli, such as nature sounds and instrumental music [30].

This section describes the initial prototype for an app designed to promote sleep. The prototype presents sounds tailored to the user's emotional state. Research has shown that visual experiences are important to induce relaxation by providing a sense of restoration and a reduction in tension [31]. Therefore, the prototype design paid considerable attention to the visual aspects. Additionally, user-centered design principles [32] are utilized to ensure a calming and pleasant user experience. Moraveji and Soesanto [33] propose 10 design heuristics used to minimize the number of stressors in an interface. These include: (1) reducing feeling overwhelmed by presenting as little data as possible; (2) using appropriate tone and emotions such as being polite and apologetic; (3) providing positive feedback to user input such as "Thank you for filling out the form", and (4) relieving time pressure. Furthermore, a screen dark mode makes it comfortable for users to use their mobiles at night or in the dark [34].

In this prototype, the user is asked to choose their current emotional state from the four emotions used in the survey. Based on the user's responses, the application suggests sounds to be played to enhance sleep. The sound suggestions are based on the results of the survey described in 4. Furthermore, the user can preview the sounds before selecting the final one. The app prioritizes ease of interaction making it as simple as possible for the user to engage

Figure 3. This figure displays three screenshots from the prototype of the sleep enhancement application designed to assist users in selecting sounds based on their emotional state to improve sleep quality.

with the interface and avoid confusion before sleeping. It provides simple visual cues for user guidance and feedback. For instance, when the user clicks on a sound button, the color of the border changes, indicating that the sound is playing. Font type and size are chosen to avoid straining the eyes while reading under low light conditions.

7. DISCUSSION

This study aims to investigate the relationship between emotional state and the sounds people choose to aid their sleep. The results of the survey show that people seem to prefer different sounds for sleep depending on their emotional state.

For negative emotions (Stressed and Sad), Rain, Underwater, and Singing Bowl sounds were preferred. Rain and Underwater are natural sounds with slow tempos, and the Singing Bowl sound is musical with low-pitch characteristics.

For positive emotions (Happy and Calm), Rain, Birds and Crickets sounds were preferred. These sounds are relatively noisy natural sounds, with soft volumes and little loudness variation, but with a relatively high frequency content when compared to the Underwater and Singing Bowl sounds.

The study seems to indicate that the frequency content of a sound plays a role in what sounds people choose depending on their emotional state.

7.1 Sound ranking

Most participants generally rated Underwater sounds high for negative emotions. However, some participant experienced anxiety when exposed to these sounds, which highlights the importance of accounting for individual differences in sound preferences. With this in mind, the app prototype is designed to offer the possibility of choosing among several different sounds that have been shown to be liked when experiencing a specific emotion. This approach ensures that users can further select the sound that best suits their personal comfort and preferences.

In this study, we have also explored differences in relation to gender and the use of audio as a sleep aid. The results seem to indicate that there may be differences along

Figure 4. This figure displays spectrograms of the six sounds used in the survey. On the left side are spectrograms for sounds preferred during negative emotions. On the right side are the sounds preferred during positive emotions.

these categories. These could be due to how the relationship between gender and emotions is portrayed in media and culture, for example. Additionally, a person’s existing experience with audio as a sleep aid might mean that they already know that certain sounds, associations, etc. will not work for soothing or maintaining a particular emotion for them (for example, a person might like the Underwater sound in normal circumstances, but they have used it once to go to sleep and they know that it can bring up bad memories about an experience with water and therefore know that they would not choose it). A larger study specifically designed to examine these differences would need to be carried out to confirm the findings and explore any underlying reasons for this.

The main limitations of the study can be summarized as follows. The sounds were selected on the basis of prior research on sound characteristics that help to reach a relaxed, positive state. However, it is possible that not all participants found that the chosen sounds fit these characteristics. For instance, the pitch and tempo of the Chimes sound were not perceived as pleasant or serene as anticipated. One participant described the sound as *“Too loud and aggressive to be calming,”* adding, *“if I’m already calm, I’d prefer something more chill, like rain”*.

Some differences in choices were observed between the two groups. For example, Local Group preferred the Crickets sound more than the Global Group. We suggest that a cultural difference could be the reason for this. Crickets are not common in cold weather and some can only be heard during summer in Sweden. For some people from the Local Group, Crickets reminded them of summertime on the beach, perhaps in another country, which helped them calm down. This association may be less significant for people from other countries and cultures. Finally, for some participants, the Birds sound was associated with the morning and therefore they felt it not to be suitable as an aid for going to sleep since that usually happens at night. Future studies should explore a more comprehensive collection of sounds for each category and allow participants to select

from multiple instances of each sound category.

Another limitation of this study is the fact that we asked people to “imagine” feeling an emotion before going to sleep, rather than survey them when they go to sleep and feel a specific emotion. This second and more realistic option requires a longitudinal study that is very demanding in terms of time and resources. Our study was designed as a pilot that could reveal whether the research focus would warrant a larger, longitudinal, more in-depth study. In this sense, this study is successful in suggesting that this research direction is worthy of further investigation.

Further limitations include a relatively small participants’ sample, a limited age range, and a limited number of emotions, which again should be addressed in a larger, future study.

7.2 Future work

A further study is underway, where participants are asked to use the “SoundAsleep” app before going to sleep. The study is carried out at home and lasts for a minimum of one week. The app provides participants with several sounds to choose from for each emotion to ensure that individual differences can be observed. The emotional states and sound choices are tracked by the researchers. In addition, each morning, participants are asked to provide feedback on the chosen sound and their sleep through a sleep diary. Finally, participants are asked to answer questions about the app’s effectiveness and user-experience.

8. CONCLUSION

The study investigates the relationship between emotional states and sound preferences as a sleep aid. The study achieved this by conducting an online survey asking participants to rank their sound preferences for sleep according to a particular emotional state they were asked to imagine feeling. The emotional states were Happy, Stressed, Calm, and Sad. Participants were recruited into two groups: one from a close network and another group recruited online. The results from the survey show that there appears to be a relationship between emotional states and sound preferences as a sleep aid. The results indicate distinct preferences for certain types of sounds based on emotional state, with sounds such as Rain, Underwater, and Singing Bowls preferred by individuals experiencing negative emotions. At the same time, Birds and Crickets sounds were more often preferred for positive emotional states. The results also show similarities between the two different groups recruited for data collection. The application prototype presented in this paper is designed to be easy to use and calming, while offering users the choice between three different sounds depending on their emotional state before going to bed.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by the EU MSCA Lullabyte Doctoral Network <https://lullabyte.eu>.

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